

A weakened AMOC could cause Southern Ocean temperature and sea-ice change on multidecadal timescales

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Key Points:

- We present the first CMIP6 multi-model intercomparison of AMOC weakening impacts on Southern Ocean temperatures and sea ice.
- Increased southwards heat transport into the Southern Ocean causes warming and sea-ice loss, smaller than direct climate forcing effects.
- We find a novel, tropical-Antarctic atmospheric teleconnection, which causes regional temperature and sea-ice change.

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Abstract

We present the first CMIP6-era multi-model intercomparison of the Southern Ocean temperature and sea-ice response to substantial AMOC weakening. Results are based on analysis of the North Atlantic Hosing Model Intercomparison Project (NAHosMIP), involving eight CMIP6 models under identical North Atlantic freshwater hosing. On multidecadal timescales, we find that southwards ocean heat transport into the Southern Ocean increases, causing surface warming and sea-ice loss. Additionally, an atmospheric tropical-Antarctic teleconnection, identified here for the first time, causes regional temperature and sea-ice changes in the Southern Ocean. Unlike previous studies, we find that the Amundsen Sea Low deepens for only some models. Overall, in the multi-model ensemble mean (multi-model range in brackets), over years 50-100 after AMOC weakening: Southern Ocean surface air temperature warms by 0.3 (0.1–0.7)°C, sea level pressure decreases by 30 (10–70)Pa, and sea-ice area decreases by 0.4 (–0.2–1.3)Mkm². The teleconnection leads to regional differences between the response in the Indian sector and the Weddell Sea, of 180 (80–320)Pa in sea level pressure, 0.6 (0.5–1.4)°C in surface air temperature, and 0.1 (0.1–0.2)Mkm² in sea-ice area. These Southern Ocean heat transport, temperature, pressure, and sea-ice changes are small relative to the changes expected under future anthropogenic warming, despite the large and idealised 0.3 Sv hosing used to weaken the AMOC.

Plain Language Summary

The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) could substantially weaken over the next century due to climate change. The Southern Ocean is a key control of global ocean circulation and climate. Here, we use the latest generation of climate models to assess the impacts of this potential AMOC weakening on the Southern Ocean and Antarctic sea ice, on timescales of less than a century. Following AMOC weakening, ocean transports move heat southwards into the Southern Ocean, causing Southern Ocean surface warming and sea-ice loss. We also identify a new atmospheric connection, from the tropics to Antarctica: this connection enhances warming and sea-ice loss in one Southern Ocean region, but causes cooling and sea-ice growth in another. This shows that substantial AMOC weakening could impact the Southern Ocean on multidecadal timescales. However, these Southern Ocean changes resulting from AMOC collapse are much smaller than the projected direct impacts of greenhouse-gas-induced warming.

1 Introduction

The crucial importance of the Southern Ocean (SO) for global climate has been highlighted in recent years. The SO accounts for most of the excess heat and carbon absorbed by the global ocean under anthropogenic climate change, alleviating short-term atmospheric warming (Gruber et al., 2019; Sallée, 2018). Furthermore, SO sea ice exerts a strong control on the global ocean circulation (Ferrari et al., 2014; Carter et al., 2008), but processes governing its recent variations are not well understood (Eayrs et al., 2021; Meehl et al., 2019; Purich & Doddridge, 2023; Diamond et al., 2024; Jena et al., 2024).

The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) forms part of the global ocean circulation system. It is the Atlantic Ocean’s primary overturning current system, and transports warm water northwards in the upper ocean, and cold water southwards in the deeper ocean (Buckley & Marshall, 2016; Fox-Kemper et al., 2021). Within the 21st century, AMOC weakening is ‘very likely’, due to Atlantic Ocean warming, alongside freshening from Northern Hemisphere meltwater (Fox-Kemper et al., 2021). There is ‘medium confidence’ that an abrupt collapse will not occur before 2100 (Fox-Kemper et al., 2021), but it is still a possibility (Sgubin et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2017). It is therefore vital to understand the potential impacts of a substantial weakening or shutdown

87 of the AMOC (Orihuela-Pinto et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2020; Buckley & Marshall, 2016;
88 Bellomo et al., 2021; Jackson et al., 2015).

89 One of the largest impacts of the AMOC on climate is through its transport of heat
90 from the Southern to Northern Hemisphere (Buckley & Marshall, 2016; Zhang et al., 2017).
91 A weakened (strengthened) AMOC would weaken (strengthen) this northward heat trans-
92 port (Chiang & Bitz, 2005; Krebs & Timmermann, 2007; Stocker et al., 2007; Laurian
93 & Drijfhout, 2011; Zhang et al., 2017). This would cause Northern Hemisphere cooling
94 (warming) (Krebs & Timmermann, 2007; Broccoli et al., 2006) and Southern Hemisphere
95 warming (cooling) (Crowley, 1992; Stocker & Johnsen, 2003; Stocker et al., 2007; Lau-
96 rian & Drijfhout, 2011). The ‘bipolar seesaw’ mechanism describes this balancing of heat
97 between hemispheres, controlled by AMOC strength (Stocker & Johnsen, 2003; Stocker
98 et al., 2007). Specifically, a reduced AMOC, particularly the weakening of South Atlantic
99 currents that transport warm waters equatorward, would lead to heat accumulation in
100 the South Atlantic and north of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC) (Stocker et
101 al., 2007; Timmermann et al., 2007). This has been linked to a weakened North Brazil
102 Current and altered heat transport pathways (Timmermann et al., 2007; Laurian & Dri-
103 jfhout, 2011), resulting in ocean warming north of the ACC (Timmermann et al., 2007;
104 Laurian & Drijfhout, 2011; Orihuela-Pinto et al., 2022). Over timescales of centuries, these
105 ocean heat anomalies are gradually advected southward and mix across the ACC (Pedro
106 et al., 2018).

107 Palaeoclimate records support this mechanism: in Arctic ice cores, a ‘Dansgaard-
108 Oeschger (DO) event’ during the last glacial period is marked by a rapid transition from
109 a cool ‘stadial’ weak-AMOC state, to a warm ‘interstadial’ strong-AMOC state, and sub-
110 sequent slow cooling back to a stadial (Gottschalk et al., 2015; Menviel et al., 2020; Thomas
111 et al., 2009; Dansgaard et al., 1993; Malmierca-Vallet & Sime, 2023). Each DO event is
112 associated with an Antarctic Isotope Maximum (AIM) event: AMOC weakening dur-
113 ing DO events is associated with Antarctic warming, lagged by one to two centuries (Svensson
114 et al., 2020; WAIS-Divide-Members, 2015; Markle et al., 2017). The ‘*thermal* bipolar see-
115 saw’ mechanism explains the lag in terms of a slow heat build-up in a Southern Hemi-
116 sphere oceanic heat reservoir that modulates and delays the Antarctic temperature re-
117 sponse (Stocker & Johnsen, 2003; WAIS-Divide-Members, 2015; Buizert et al., 2018; Landais
118 et al., 2015). These linked DO and AIM events indicate how, on centennial timescales,
119 AMOC changes imprint themselves on the SO and Antarctica, as supported by model
120 studies, e.g. Brown and Galbraith (2016); Liu et al. (2017); Pedro et al. (2018).

121 However, we note the SO response to substantial AMOC weakening may differ un-
122 der present-day (rather than glacial) conditions (Timmermann et al., 2010). Further-
123 more, the timing and magnitude of the SO response remains uncertain, particularly at
124 shorter-than-centennial timescales. Some evidence exists for dynamic multidecadal-scale
125 atmospheric responses. These may include a poleward shift of the Southern Hemisphere
126 westerlies (Chen et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2017; Markle et al., 2017) linked to a more po-
127 sitive Southern Annular Mode (SAM) (Yuan & Li, 2008; Rind et al., 2018, 2001; Tim-
128 mermann et al., 2010). Furthermore, tropical-Antarctic teleconnections may lead to fast
129 pressure changes over the SO, including deepening the Amundsen Sea Low (ASL) (Orihuela-
130 Pinto et al., 2022; Timmermann et al., 2010).

131 Thus far, no near-present-day studies of AMOC weakening show multidecadal-scale
132 Antarctic sea-ice change. The expected sea-ice behaviour is unclear, given the combined
133 potential influences on the sea ice of ocean and/or atmospheric warming (Liu et al., 2020;
134 Pedro et al., 2018; Orihuela-Pinto et al., 2022; Timmermann et al., 2010), and atmospheric
135 changes including a more positive phase SAM (Zhang et al., 2017; Guarino et al., 2023;
136 Rind et al., 2001), and deepened ASL (Timmermann et al., 2010; Orihuela-Pinto et al.,
137 2022).

Table 1. List of global climate models used in this study, and their associated atmospheric, ocean and sea-ice components.

Model	Atm model	Ocean model	Ice model	Reference
HadGEM3-GC3-1LL	UM GA7	NEMO3.6	CICE GSI8.1	Williams et al. (2018)
HadGEM3-GC3-1MM	UM GA7	NEMO3.6	CICE GSI8.1	Williams et al. (2018)
CanESM5	CanAM5	NEMO3.4.1	LIM2	Swart et al. (2019)
EC-Earth3	IFS 36r4	NEMO3.6	LIM3	Döscher et al. (2021)
CESM2	CAM6	POP2	CICE5	Danabasoglu et al. (2020)
IPSL-CM6A-LR	LMDZ6	NEMO3.6	LIM3	Boucher et al. (2020)
MPI-ESM-LR	ECHAM6.3	MPIOM	MPIOM	Mauritsen et al. (2019)
MPI-ESM-HR	ECHAM6.3	MPIOM	MPIOM	Müller et al. (2018)

138 Given the importance of SO processes (Sallée, 2018; Shi et al., 2021; Li et al., 2023)
139 and the concern over AMOC weakening, we must understand potential impacts of sub-
140 substantial AMOC weakening on the SO and Antarctic sea ice under sub-centennial timescales
141 and near-present-day conditions. To address this, here, we investigate results for the SO
142 from the newly released North Atlantic Hosing Model Intercomparison Project, ‘NAHos-
143 MIP’ (Jackson et al., 2023). An idealised freshwater forcing was applied identically in
144 eight CMIP6-era models over the North Atlantic, significantly weakening the AMOC (Fig.
145 S1). We focus on the SO for the first 100 years, to better understand mechanisms of rapid
146 change, and the balance between oceanic and atmospheric responses.

147 The structure of this study is as follows. In Sec. 3.1, we present a multi-model in-
148 tercomparison of AMOC weakening impacts on global temperatures, and SO temper-
149 atures and sea ice. We show the SO response is dominated by warming and sea-ice melt,
150 but includes a temperature dipole associated with Weddell Sea cooling and sea-ice growth.
151 In Sec. 3.2, we focus on ocean and atmosphere heat transport changes, and ocean cir-
152 culation changes, to determine the drivers of SO warming. In Sec. 3.3, we investigate
153 atmospheric changes, and determine the drivers of Weddell Sea cooling. Finally, in Sec.
154 3.4, we draw together Secs. 3.2 and 3.3 to explain the patterns of temperature and sea-
155 ice change identified in Sec. 3.1.

156 2 Methods

157 2.1 Model Simulations

158 Details of the eight latest-generation climate models used in this study are shown
159 in Tables 1 and S1. The two simulations for each model used are the pre-industrial con-
160 trol (‘piControl’) experiment and the ‘u03hos’ experiment. piControl is a core experi-
161 ment run by all groups that contributed to the sixth Coupled Model Intercomparison
162 Project CMIP6 (Eyring et al., 2016). The piControl simulation uses invariant solar, green-
163 house gases, ozone, tropospheric aerosol, volcanic and land-use forcing from the year 1850
164 for the whole simulation. The u03hos experiment is part of NAHosMIP (Jackson et al.,
165 2023): the simulation is initialised from piControl with identical boundary conditions.
166 In the u03hos experiments, an additional uniform, idealised, virtual negative salinity flux
167 (‘hosing’) is applied to the North Atlantic and Arctic surface ocean, from 50°N to the
168 Bering Strait, with hosing strength of 0.3 Sv ($1 \text{ Sv} = 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), for minimum 100 years,
169 see Jackson and Wood (2018b); Jackson et al. (2023) for details. This results in signif-
170 icant AMOC weakening for all models (Jackson et al., 2023): there is an abrupt weak-

171 ening over the first few decades, that transitions to a more gradual decrease over the sub-
 172 sequent decades (Fig. S1)

173 **2.1.1 Model selection**

174 Of the eight CMIP6-era models that ran the u03hos simulation, three models (HadGEM3-
 175 GC3.1-MM, MPI-ESM1.2-LR and -HR) have especially frequent spurious deep convec-
 176 tion in the SO Weddell Sea, a model artifact common in CMIP5-era and some CMIP6-
 177 era models (Heuzé, 2021; Mohrmann et al., 2021). This leads to very frequent forma-
 178 tion of large open-water polynyas in the simulated Weddell Sea sea ice, impacting SO
 179 conditions, particularly in the Weddell Sea (Heuzé, 2021; Mohrmann et al., 2021). The
 180 focus of our work is on the SO under near-present-day conditions, and including all the
 181 models in the multi-model ensemble mean would induce spurious signals in the regions
 182 of deep convection of some of the models. Therefore, we calculate multi-model ensem-
 183 ble results (shown in Sec. 3.1) using the five models without this artifact (CanESM5,
 184 CESM2, EC-Earth3, HadGEM3-GC3.1-LL, and IPSL-CM6A-LR). However, we found
 185 that the global-scale response to hosing is similar whether considering the five non-convecting,
 186 or all eight, models. Therefore, for interest, we show results including the additional three
 187 convecting models from Sec 3.2.1 onwards.

188 **2.2 Analysis**

189 All model output variables were aggregated to a regular 1° latitude-longitude grid
 190 using the Climate Data Operators library (Schulzweida, 2023) for inter-model compar-
 191 ison. We determine the impact of freshwater hosing in the u03hos simulations by compar-
 192 ing them to the piControl simulations as follows. For all maps, unless otherwise in-
 193 dicated, we present the time-mean of the u03hos simulation over years 50-100, with the
 194 time-mean of the piControl simulation over the same period subtracted. As the simu-
 195 lations are all between 100 and 200 years long, year 50-100 is the final 50-year period that
 196 can be compared across models. By year 50-100, the AMOC is substantially weakened
 197 for all models (Fig. S1). For timeseries, unless otherwise indicated, we show the u03hos
 198 simulation result with the piControl simulation result subtracted, year by year, as in Andrews
 199 et al. (2019), to account for unforced model drift in the simulations without assuming
 200 the drift is linear. We hereafter refer to the difference between the u03hos and piCon-
 201 trol simulations as the ‘u03hos–piControl anomaly’. For a given model, the u03hos and
 202 piControl simulation outputs are compared using a t-test. Unhatched regions on maps
 203 show results statistically significant at the $p < 0.05$ level.

204 In Sec. 3.1 we identify in the u03hos simulations, relative to the piControl simu-
 205 lations, SO dipoles in SLP, SAT, and SIC. We define the ‘dipole magnitude’ as the dif-
 206 ference between the high and low centres in the dipoles as follows. For all variables, we
 207 begin with the multi-model ensemble mean of the u03hos–piControl anomaly, for all lat-
 208 itudes and longitudes over the SO region (south of 30°S), using annual means for years
 209 0–100. For SLP and SAT, to identify the locations of the high and low centres, we first
 210 identify the two grid-cells with the maximum and minimum values over the full 100 years.
 211 We then take the means over the 3×3 matrix of 1° grid-cells around each of these two
 212 grid-cell centres, and then find the difference between the two means to yield the ‘dipole
 213 magnitude’ for each variable. For SIC, we could use the same method as is used for SLP
 214 and SAT, but the following method yields a more physically meaningful quantity: for
 215 SIC, the ‘dipole magnitude’ is simply the difference in SIA between the Weddell Sea (60°W –
 216 0°E) and west Indian (0°E – 60°E) sectors (both methods yield similar results after nor-
 217 malisation).

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2.2.1 OHT and AHT

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Meridional heat transport (MHT) across a given latitude band is the sum of net ocean heat transport (OHT) and atmospheric heat transport (AHT) across the band. We use the CMIP6 diagnostic ‘hfbasin’ for OHT, and calculate AHT from the divergence of the vertical fluxes integrated over the atmosphere (equal to the sum of the AHT and atmospheric heat storage, but annual and longer-term-mean atmospheric heat storage is negligible) (Liu et al., 2018; Donohoe et al., 2020).

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2.2.2 Ocean circulation and heat transport

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In Sec. 3.2.2, we consider meridional ocean heat transport and circulation. The net (or ‘residual’) meridional overturning circulation is composed of the Deacon (Eulerian-mean) cell, compensated by the eddy-induced circulation (Danabasoglu et al., 1994; Marshall & Speer, 2012). Their respective streamfunctions are given by ψ_{res} , $\bar{\psi}$, ψ^* such that

$$\psi_{res} = \bar{\psi} + \psi^* \quad (1)$$

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The meridional OHT is the sum of contributions from this Eulerian-mean flow $\overline{OHT_{eul}}$, eddies OHT_{ed}^* and diffusion OHT_{diff} (Yang et al., 2015; Li et al., 2022):

$$OHT = \overline{OHT_{eul}} + OHT_{ed}^* + OHT_{diff} \quad (2)$$

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For parametrisations of mesoscale advection and diffusion, all models use the Gent-McWilliams scheme, with formulations from Gent and McWilliams (1990) and Redi (1982) or the formulation from Griffies (1998). For CESM2 and HadGEM3-GC3.1-LL, relevant for Sec. 3.2.2, Table S2 shows parametrisations of mesoscale advection and diffusion, sub-mesoscale eddy processes (Fox-Kemper et al., 2011), and background vertical diffusion (Large et al., 1994; Madec et al., 2013, 2017). Table 3, Jackson et al. (2023), details these parametrisations for all models. For all models, the parametrised eddy-induced advective transport ψ^* follows (Gent & McWilliams, 1990):

$$\psi^* = K * S \quad (3)$$

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where K is the eddy-induced transfer coefficient and S is the slope of the isopycnals.

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2.2.3 SAM and ASL index

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The dimensionless SAM index is (Gong & Wang, 1999):

$$SAM = P_{40}^* - P_{65}^* \quad (4)$$

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where P_{lat}^* is the normalised zonally averaged sea level pressure (SLP) at this latitude, computed from the zonally averaged SLP timeseries P_{lat} :

$$P_{lat}^*(t) = \frac{P_{lat}(t) - \mu_{P_{lat}}}{\sigma_{P_{lat}}} \quad (5)$$

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where $\mu_{P_{lat}}$ is the time-mean of the timeseries. To compute $\sigma_{P_{lat}}$, the standard deviation of the timeseries, we apply a high-pass second-order forward-backward Butterworth filter with cut-off period of 50 years to remove any long-term trend, and calculate the standard deviation from this filtered timeseries (this step changes the standard deviation value by $< 5\%$ in most and $< 15\%$ in all cases).

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The ASL index is the minimum Pacific sector SLP (60° – 75° S and 180° – 310° E; Turner et al., 2013). For easier inter-model comparison, the ASL timeseries is normalised (as described above for SLP: using the ASL timeseries long-term mean and standard deviation).

Figure 1. Multi-model mean of u03hos-piControl anomaly, taken over years 50-100 of run. Unhatched regions: agreement for at least 4 of the 5 models on sign change. (a) global SAT (b) global SLP (with zonal mean subtracted at each latitude, to show meridional variation) (c) SO SLP, with zonal mean subtracted at each latitude (contours), overlaid with surface wind vectors (d) SO SAT (e) SO sea ice concentration.

254 To estimate the sign of the response of the SAM and ASL indices in the u03hos
 255 simulations, we fit a linear trend, using a least-squares linear regression model (Virtanen
 256 et al., 2020). This returns the slope of the regression line, the standard error of this es-
 257 timated slope, and the p-value that no trend exists (calculated using a hypothesis test
 258 with null hypothesis that the slope is zero, using a Wald Test with t-distribution of the
 259 test statistic).

Figure 2. u03hos–piControl anomaly, for each model, of (a–e) global SAT, mean over final 50 years (see Table S1 for simulation lengths); and SO, mean over years 50–100 for (f–j) SAT and (k–o) SIC. Blue: piControl and red: u03hos sea-ice edge (threshold where SIC > 0.15)

3 Results

3.1 Southern Ocean temperature and sea-ice response

For all models, the AMOC weakens significantly over the first 50 years of the u03hos simulation, to a new, weaker, state (Fig. S1 for timeseries of AMOC strength; see also Jackson et al. (2023)). We consider first the response in the multi-model mean. Fig. 1(a) shows strong Northern Hemisphere cooling and weaker Southern Hemisphere warming: the well-established ‘bipolar seesaw’ pattern (e.g. Stocker and Johnsen (2003); Stocker et al. (2007); Timmermann et al. (2007)). From Fig. 1(b,c), we note in the Southern Hemisphere a ‘Rossby-wave-train’-like pattern, originating from central America and propagating south- and eastwards to the Southern Ocean (SO), investigated in Sec. 3.3.2. This pattern includes low/high sea level pressure (SLP) centres over the Atlantic/Indian SO sectors. Considering the SO response: overall, SO SAT increases (Fig. 1(d)), leading to reduced SLP (not shown) and reduced sea-ice concentration (Fig. 1(e)). The previously-identified low/high SLP centres (Fig. 1(b,c)) are associated with cyclonic/anticyclonic winds and regional temperature and sea-ice change (Figs 1(d,e)) further detailed in Sec. 3.3). Over years 50-100, in the multi-model ensemble mean (multi-model range), the overall SO SLP is reduced by 31 (6 – 72)Pa, SAT is increased by 0.29 (0.13 – 0.69) $^{\circ}$ C, and SIA is reduced by 0.40 (-0.15 – 1.32) Mkm^2 . We define the ‘dipole magnitude’ as the difference between the high and low centres of SLP, SAT, and SIA visible in Figs 1(c-e) (detailed in Sec. 2.2). The SLP dipole magnitude is 180 (80 – 320)Pa, the SAT dipole magnitude is 0.56 (0.46 – 1.35) $^{\circ}$ C, and the SIA dipole magnitude is 0.10 (0.05 – 0.18) Mkm^2 . Timeseries of all these quantities over years 0–100 are shown in Fig. S2. In the Ross and Amundsen Sea regions, SLP decreases by up to 30Pa (Fig. 1(b,c)), and Amundsen Sea SIC decreases by 2-8%.

We now consider the Southern Hemisphere response by individual model (see also Figs S3–S6). In the Southern Hemisphere, northwards of the SO (0° to 30° S), all models eventually warm over all sectors, by 0.1 to 1.5 $^{\circ}$ C (Figs 2(a-e)). The magnitude of the warming differs between models, with strongest warming for CESM2, and weakest for EC-Earth3.

We move on to the response in the SO region (30° to 90° S), shown in Figs 2(f-j). The Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC) warms for all models, over all sectors, particularly in the Indian sector at 200m–1km depth (see also Figs S7–S9). Southwards of the ACC, there is regional warming for all models, particularly in the Indian sector. We note IPSL-CM6A-LR has some Pacific sector cooling, similar to some CMIP3 and CMIP5 models under freshwater hosing (Timmermann et al., 2010; Buiron et al., 2012).

Fig. 2(k-o) shows the u03hos-piControl sea-ice concentration (SIC) anomaly; this broadly matches the SAT anomaly where sea-ice exists. All models have statistically significant ice loss, with maximum regional SIC reductions ranging from 5 to 25% across models. Regions of greater sea-ice loss (\sim 10 to 20%) have especially high SATs; see e.g. CESM2 and HadGEM3-GC3.1-LL, with SAT increases of 1.5 $^{\circ}$ –3 $^{\circ}$ C in the regions of greatest sea-ice loss, likely linked to ice-albedo feedbacks (Curry et al., 1995). Despite ice loss in other regions, Weddell Sea SIC (and ice thickness, not shown) either increases, or does not change, for 4/5 models.

To summarise, all models have Southern Hemisphere warming (and Northern Hemisphere cooling). By years 50-100, warming extends to the SO Indian sector for all models, especially along the ACC at \sim 200-500m depth. For most models, sea ice is reduced particularly in the Indian sector, but in the Weddell Sea there is regional cooling and sea-ice growth. Over years 50-100, in the multi-model ensemble mean, the SO SLP decreases by 31 Pa, SAT increases by 0.29 $^{\circ}$ C, and SIA decreases by 0.40 Mkm^2 . The difference between the Indian sector and Weddell Sea response in SLP is 180 Pa, in SAT is 0.56 $^{\circ}$ C, and in SIA is 0.1 Mkm^2 .

Figure 3. u03hos–piControl anomaly for each model (from time-means taken over years 50–100 of each simulation), for (a): meridional ocean heat transport, and (b): meridional atmospheric heat transport. Dotted vertical lines: approximate winter piControl sea-ice edge latitude for each model (latitude where mean SIC>0.05)

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3.2 Drivers of Southern Ocean warming

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Here, we determine what drives warming north of the ACC and explain how this heat crosses the ACC, leading to warming at high SO latitudes. We first investigate oceanic and atmospheric heat transport changes for all models, then move onto a more detailed analysis of ocean circulation and heat transport changes for two models.

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3.2.1 OHT and AHT: all models

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Fig. 3 shows the u03hos–piControl anomaly of meridional OHT and AHT for all models (see Fig. S10(a–b) for time-means of meridional OHT and AHT, for all models, for both u03hos and piControl simulations). In the u03hos simulations, compared to the piControl simulations, there is increased southwards OHT from the equator up to the ACC for all models (Fig. 3(a) and S10(a)). Considering all 8 models, we find a statistically significant ($p=0.01$) correlation between the AMOC strength change and the magnitude of the southwards OHT change into the SO (Fig. 4(a)), i.e. models with greater AMOC reduction tend to have a greater increase in southwards OHT into the SO.

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All models have southwards OHT through the equatorwards portion of the ACC (the Subantarctic Front, approximately 40° – 50° S); for 6 out of 8 there is also southwards OHT through the ACC (up to $\sim 60^{\circ}$ S), and for all models there is southwards OHT polewards of the winter sea-ice edge and up to Antarctica. This increase in southwards OHT across the ACC and up to Antarctica occurs on multidecadal timescales for all models (Fig. S11).

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This begins to explain the SO warming across models: due to the AMOC weakening and heat build-up in the Southern Hemisphere ocean interior (Figs S7–9), ocean transports redistribute this heat southwards, increasing SO SSTs and SATs. There is an increase in northwards AHT at most latitudes for all models (Figs 3(b) and S12). We explain the sign of the AHT change in terms of Bjerknes compensation: a change to the meridional OHT is balanced by an approximately equal and opposite change to the meridional AHT, and vice versa, to retain a similar total meridional heat transport (Bjerknes, 1964; Swingedouw et al., 2009). Therefore, over the Southern Hemisphere, northwards AHT increases to balance the increased southwards OHT, most likely due to a strengthened Hadley Cell (Yang et al., 2013).

Figure 4. For each model, calculated from the u03hos–piControl anomaly mean over years 50–100: change in (a) mean southwards OHT between 30°S and 55°S, against AMOC weakening, calculated from maximum streamfunction at 26.5°N (x-axis). Black line for each plot: linear fit from least-squares regression. Blue shaded region: error of linear fit, calculated by propagating the errors returned on fitted gradient and intercept.

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3.2.2 Heat transports in detail: two models

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We compare CESM2 and HadGEM3-GC3.1-LL (with similar sea-ice components, but different atmosphere and ocean components). We select these models as both show SO warming and sea-ice loss, but CESM2 has the strongest response of all models, while HadGEM3-GC3.1-LL represents the multi-model mean ensemble behaviour well (Figs 1, 2 and S1). In Sec. 3.2.1, we identified, in the u03hos compared to the piControl simulations, increased southwards OHT across the ACC that acts to warm high SO latitudes. We explain this in terms of ocean circulation and heat accumulation changes.

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The SH westerlies induce northwards Ekman transport in the SO (Marshall & Speer, 2012), shown in Fig. 5(d) as the northwards ocean meridional velocity in the surface ocean between 40° and 60°S. This drives the Deacon cell $\bar{\psi}$ (black contours in Fig. 5(e,g)), with northwards flow at the ocean surface (above $\sim 100\text{m}$), and southwards flow in the subsurface (below $\sim 100\text{m}$). In Sec. 3.3, we show that the AMOC weakening leads to a polewards shift of the SH westerlies. This polewards shift of the westerlies shifts the region of Ekman transport polewards (Fig. 5(d)), shifting the Deacon cell polewards (visible as a dipole pattern of change in Fig. 5(e)), as in e.g. Bouttes et al. (2012); Chen et al. (2019). This polewards shift of the Deacon cell steepens the isohalines, particularly over 45°–65°S (Fig. 5(b)). The steepened isohalines (a reasonable approximation of the isopycnals in this region, Talley (2013); Sallée et al. (2010)) increase baroclinic instability. This strengthens the eddy circulation ψ^* , particularly over 45°–65°S, from the surface to several kilometres’ depth (Fig. 5(d)). The strengthened eddy circulation largely compensates the Deacon cell strengthening over 55°–65°S. Overall, the SO meridional overturning circulation ψ_{res} weakens on the equatorward flank and strengthens on the poleward flank (Fig. S13(a)). HadGEM-GC3.1-LL has a similar ψ_{res} change (Fig. S13(b)).

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AMOC weakening reduces northwards heat transport in the south Atlantic (Stocker et al., 2007; Timmermann et al., 2007). This leads to heat accumulation in the SH ocean

Figure 5. All panels show CESM2 ocean zonal mean over years 50-100, with black contours: piControl, overlaid with coloured contours: u03hos-piControl anomaly (except where indicated otherwise). Vertical dotted line: mean piControl winter sea-ice edge identified as in Fig. 3. (a, b, e, f) show ocean at all depths; (c, d, g, h) show upper 200m of ocean only. Variables shown are: (a, c) ocean potential temperature (b) ocean salinity (d) ocean meridional velocity (for this panel only, coloured contours show absolute value in u03hos simulation) (e, g) Eulerian-mean circulation (f, h) eddy circulation.

Figure 6. All panels show meridional OHT, mean over years 50-100, with black: total OHT; grey: Eulerian-mean heat transport; yellow: eddy-induced advective heat transport; red: diffusive heat transport; dotted vertical line: approx. winter sea-ice edge position identified as in Fig. 3. (a-b) heat transport, from piControl (dotted lines) and u03hos (solid lines), for (a) CESM2 and (b) HadGEM3-GC3.1-LL. (c-d) u03hos-piControl heat transport anomaly, for (c) CESM2 and (d) HadGEM3-GC3.1-LL.

367 interior, with the greatest positive ocean potential temperature anomaly north of the ACC,
 368 from the surface to 1km depth (Fig. 5(a, c); Figs S8-9). Temperature at deeper ocean
 369 levels does not change significantly, so the vertical potential temperature gradient north
 370 of the ACC increases. The eddy-induced circulation is strengthened, and net southwards
 371 from the surface to ~ 1 km depth (Fig. 5(f, h)). Therefore, the eddy-induced circulation
 372 acts to advect the positive heat anomaly, over 0-1km depth, southwards across the ACC,
 373 shown as increased southwards eddy heat transport (Fig. 6(c-d), 40° – 60° S). Furthermore,
 374 this temperature anomaly north of the ACC increases the meridional temperature gra-
 375 dient across the ACC. Therefore, in addition to the previously discussed increased eddy
 376 heat transport, southwards diffusive OHT also increases across the ACC (Fig. 6(c-d),
 377 50° – 60° S).

378 The Eulerian-mean OHT is the net effect of a northward transport of heat in the
 379 surface (above ~ 100 m) and a southward transport of heat in the subsurface (below ~ 100 m).
 380 The southwards heat transport dominates over most latitudes, but the strong northwards
 381 Ekman flow leads to net northwards OHT between 40° and 50° S, from Fig. 6(a,b) and
 382 Yang et al. (2015). In the u03hos relative to the piControl simulations, there is a dipole
 383 pattern in the Eulerian-mean OHT (Fig. 6(c,d)): increased southwards OHT from approx.
 384 30° – 50° S, and increased northwards OHT from approx. 50° – 60° S (partially com-
 385 pensating the increase in southwards eddy and diffusive heat transports over this region).
 386 This OHT dipole pattern is partly explained by the dipole pattern in the Deacon cell
 387 change (Fig. 5(f)). Specifically, the poleward shift of the westerlies and the Deacon cell
 388 results in upper-ocean warming between 30 and 50° S due to increased downwelling of
 389 warm surface waters, leading to anomalous convergence of ocean heat transport in this
 390 range (Chen et al., 2019; Fyfe et al., 2007; Bouttes et al., 2012; Liu et al., 2018; Yin et
 391 al., 2010). Additionally, AMOC weakening leads to heat accumulation in the upper ocean
 392 north of the ACC, which intensifies the latitudinal temperature gradient (Fig. 5(a,c)).
 393 This enhanced gradient also increases southward OHT, with heat advected southward
 394 and downward by the downwelling branch of the Deacon cell. Conversely, over 50° – 60° S,
 395 the anomalous ‘northwards’ heat transport is explained by the polewards-shifted Dea-
 396 con cell enhancing upwelling of cool, deep water, and divergence of heat transport (Bouttes
 397 et al., 2012). However, the centres of the two dipole patterns differ: e.g. for CESM2, they
 398 are centred respectively at 48° and 55° S. Therefore, we consider also the location of the
 399 positive heat anomaly (Fig. 5(a,c)): the ocean surface warms from 30° – 70° S, and the
 400 upper ocean warms down to ~ 1.5 km depth from 30° – 45° S. The surface-intensified warm-
 401 ing enhances northwards heat transport by the Ekman flow over 35° – 65° S. This heat trans-
 402 port change is partly compensated by the Deacon cell’s southwards branch, which ad-
 403 vects the positive heat anomaly southwards over 30° – 50° S. Therefore, overall, the Eulerian-
 404 mean OHT anomaly is southwards up to 48° S, but slightly northwards from 48° – 62° S.

405 In summary, there is increased southwards OHT into the SO region, due to the south-
 406 wards shift of the Deacon cell, coupled with the increased southwards eddy and diffu-
 407 sive OHT (partly balanced by the increased northwards AHT, and, at high latitudes, by
 408 the increased northwards Eulerian-mean OHT). This explains warming of the SO region.

409 3.3 Drivers of Southern Ocean temperature dipole

410 Here, we outline the atmospheric response: changes to sea level pressure (SLP) and
 411 winds, including the Southern Annular Mode (SAM), and Amundsen Sea Low (ASL),
 412 and other drivers of zonally asymmetric changes including tropical-Antarctic teleconnec-
 413 tions. We use this to explain the regional warming/cooling pattern in the Indian sector/Weddell
 414 Sea.

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3.3.1 SLP and wind changes

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As mentioned in Sec. 3.1, SO temperatures increase, which explains the lowered SLPs in most regions (Fig. 7). The SH subtropical highs weaken for all models by up to 2hPa (Fig. S14), in agreement with Orihuela-Pinto et al. (2022) who also noted increased SLPs to the south-west of South America, seen here for CESM2 and MPI models. However, the dominant SO feature for all models is a pressure dipole over the SO region: low/high pressure centres with associated cyclonic/anticyclonic wind anomalies over the Weddell Sea/King Hakon sea in the west of the Indian sector (Fig. 7, and previously discussed in Sec. 3.1). The locations of the pressure centres differ slightly between models, but generally lead to strengthened southwards winds towards the Weddell Sea, and strengthened northwards winds away from the Antarctic Peninsula, and from the east Antarctic. Considering all 8 models, we again find a statistically significant ($p=0.008$) correlation (Fig 4(b)) between the AMOC strength change and the pressure dipole magnitude (defined in Sec. 2.2): models with greater AMOC reduction tend to have a greater dipole magnitude.

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For all models, the Southern Hemisphere westerlies weaken on the equatorward flank. For 6/8 models (CESM2, EC-Earth3, HadGEM3-GC3.1-LL and -MM, MPI-ESM-LR and -HR), the SH westerlies are shifted polewards (Fig. S10(c,d)): specifically, the zonal winds weaken on the equatorward flank, and strengthen on the poleward flank. For 2/8 models (CanESM5 and IPSL-CM6A-LR) the westerlies slightly weaken throughout (by up to 0.1m/s). This weakening is zonally asymmetric (Fig. 7): Indian sector winds weaken the most (with some weakening in the Pacific). This is consistent with a polewards shift of the westerlies (Hu et al., 2021; Rind et al., 2018; Markle et al., 2017) and Ferrell cell (Chen et al., 2019) in response to AMOC weakening, explaining the polewards shift and strengthening of the Deacon cell in Sec. 3.2.2 (Liu et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2019). CESM2 again shows the strongest response of up to 1m/s (compared to original strengths of up to 8m/s), and most other models show weakening of order 0.5m/s.

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A polewards shift of the westerlies is generally associated with a more positive SAM. The ASL may deepen in response to AMOC weakening (Timmermann et al., 2010). The ASL is anti-correlated with the SAM and may be impacted by atmospheric teleconnections. Of the five models with more reliable SO climate (Sec. 2.1.1), four have a deepened ASL; three have a more positive SAM (Fig. S15). This is consistent with a small ($< 100Pa$) SLP reduction visible for some of the models in the Amundsen or Ross regions (Fig. S14). We obtained similar results using the relative ASL index (Hosking et al., 2013). We found no clear trend across models in location change of the ASL.

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3.3.2 Atmospheric teleconnections

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From Fig. 8(a-f), most models seem to show a Rossby wave-train-like pattern propagating from the east tropical Pacific and central America eastwards towards Antarctica. We verify this pattern is present for all models: from Fig. 8(g), the sign change of the geopotential height anomaly along the wave-train path is consistent across all models, so this pattern is present for all models. This wave-train explains the previously-identified low/high pressure anomalies over the Atlantic/Indian SO sectors.

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We highlight that the wave-train's path differs from that of previously-identified wave-trains excited by AMOC weakening (Orihuela-Pinto et al., 2022; Timmermann et al., 2010). Furthermore, the ASL is rarely in its path, so the ASL deepening shown by most models cannot be attributed to this teleconnection and must be due to other reasons (e.g. a more positive SAM).

Figure 7. u03hos-piControl anomaly SO sea level pressure mean over years 50-100 (contours). Mean wind vector anomalies over years 50-100 are overplotted as vectors; black arrows show changes significant at the $p=0.05$ level. Note different wind vector scale for CESM2.

Figure 8. (a-f) u03hos-piControl anomaly of global mean geopotential height at 200hPa (zonal mean subtracted) over years 50-100, for the six of eight models where data accessible. Unhatched regions: statistically significant at $p=0.05$ level. (g) Multi-model mean. Unhatched regions show where all models agree on change of sign.

Figure 9. (a-f) HadGEM3-GC3.1-LL u03hos-piControl anomaly of mean over years 50-100. Unhatched regions: statistically significant at $p=0.05$ level. (a) SAT [°C] (b) sea-ice thickness [m] (c) net heat flux at ocean surface; positive downwards [W/m^2] (d) longwave downwelling radiation at surface; positive downwards [W/m^2] (e) Ice volume tendency (due to thermodynamics) [cm/day] (f) Ice volume tendency (due to dynamics) [cm/day]. For (e-f): overplotted arrows indicate surface wind vector anomalies. Note also, to guide the eye, only ice volume tendency anomalies that match the sign of the sea-ice thickness anomaly, and thus could explain it, are shown. (g) attribution of sea-ice thermodynamic thickness change in (e) to heat fluxes from the ocean and/or atmosphere (shown in (c) and (d) respectively), based on the sign and magnitude of the change. For example, if a region of sea-ice melt has a more positive atmospheric downwelling longwave anomaly but the upwards ocean heat flux anomaly is negative (or negligible, defined as less than 1/10 magnitude of the longwave anomaly) the sea-ice melt is attributed to the atmospheric flux change only.

3.4 Causes of Southern Ocean temperature and sea-ice change

Here, we further explain the previously identified patterns of SO temperature and sea-ice change, in terms of the SO warming discussed in Sec. 3.2, and the SO temperature dipole discussed in Sec. 3.3. To do this, we present results for HadGEM3-GC3.1-LL, which represents the mean ensemble behaviour well. Figs 9(a-f) respectively show the u3hos-piControl anomaly of SAT, SIC, net downwards heat flux into the ocean surface (calculated at the air-sea interface, or ice-sea interface in ice-covered regions, using CMIP6 variable ‘hfds’, from Griffies et al. (2016)), downwelling longwave flux from the atmosphere at the surface (the ocean, ice, or land surface, as applicable), and the sea-ice volume tendencies due to thermodynamics and dynamics. In addition to the surface downwelling longwave flux, we also considered all other atmospheric surface heat flux terms (including shortwave and latent and sensible heat fluxes), but found that only the longwave term had a statistically significant u3hos-piControl anomaly relevant for the following analysis.

We begin with the SO warming. In Sec. 3.2, we found that AMOC weakening led to heat accumulation in the SH upper ocean, north of the ACC. This ocean heat anomaly is predominantly transported southwards through the ACC via ocean eddies and diffusion, warming the upper ocean. The ocean surface releases this excess heat to the atmosphere (Fig. 9(c)), which warms (Fig. S9). The warmed atmosphere responds by releasing heat, both upwards (not shown) and back downwards (Fig. 9(d)). Overall, air temperatures increase in most regions (Fig. 9(a)). South of the ice edge: sea-ice melts in most regions (Fig. 9(b)). This is due partly to direct ocean warming (Fig. 9(c)), and partly to the ocean warming the atmosphere north of the ice edge, so the ice surface is warmed by downwelling longwave radiation (Fig. 9(d)).

We now explain the SO temperature and sea-ice dipole in terms of the atmospheric response to AMOC weakening. From Sec. 3.3, we found that a Rossby-wave-like pattern leads to a SO pressure dipole, associated with cyclonic/anticyclonic winds (arrows in Figs 9(e,f)). Due to a combination of dynamic and thermodynamic processes (Fig. 9(e,f)), the cyclonic anomaly leads to sea-ice thickness increase in the northern Weddell Sea near the ice edge, as in Holland and Kwok (2012); Vernet et al. (2019). Near the ice edge, in the sector 0-30°W, ice thickness increases due to dynamics (Fig. 9(f)). Slightly polewards, in the ice interior, the south-westwards wind anomaly drives convergent ice drift (ridging); near the sea-ice edge, the north-westwards wind anomaly drives divergent ice drift, advecting the sea ice northwards. In the sector 30-60°W, thermodynamic processes lead to ice growth (Fig. 9(e)): at the sea-ice edge, the north-westwards wind anomaly advects relatively cool, dry air, cooling the ocean surface and resulting in additional thermodynamic ice growth; additionally we note thermodynamic ice growth in the ice interior. Conversely, south of Africa, warm, moist air is advected southwards, leading to warming, sea-ice loss, and inhibiting ice growth at the ice edge. Conversely, south of Africa, over the King Hakon low (Holland & Kwok, 2012), warm, moist air is advected southwards, leading to warming, sea-ice loss, and inhibiting ice growth at the ice edge. Furthermore, the warming/cooling pattern in the Amundsen-Bellinghousen/Ross seas and associated sea-ice loss/increase (Fig. 9(a,b)) is likely explained by the deepened ASL (Fig. S15) and associated wind anomalies (Fig. 9(c,d)).

Fig. 9(g) shows an attribution of sea-ice thermodynamic change in Fig. 9(e) to heat fluxes from the ocean or atmosphere (Figs 9(c) and (d) respectively), based on the sign and magnitude of the change. In a few areas, ice melt can be attributed primarily to only one of the atmosphere or ocean (in particular, some regions of melt are attributed to atmosphere only, in light orange). However, in most regions, melt or growth is attributed to a combination of both atmosphere and ocean change (red for melt and blue for growth) – this is especially clear in the Pacific and west Indian Sectors, and in the Weddell Sea.

513 This analysis demonstrates that the SAT and sea-ice response is determined by both
 514 ocean and atmosphere. Specifically, the response is governed both by increased south-
 515 wards OHT across the ACC and associated ocean and atmospheric warming, and by the
 516 strongly zonally asymmetric pressure dipole. Furthermore, the slightly deepened ASL
 517 likely contributes to sea-ice reduction in the Amundsen sector.

518 4 Discussion

519 Here, we investigated the multidecadal-timescale SO response to AMOC weaken-
 520 ing, using a CMIP6-era model ensemble. In particular, we focused on the SO temper-
 521 ature and sea-ice responses, which have not previously been investigated in detail. We
 522 explained the overall SO response in terms of two ‘groups’ of processes. We find an ap-
 523 proximately linear inter-model relationship between the magnitude of the AMOC weak-
 524 ening, and a key process linked to each of these two groups (Fig. 4): models with greater
 525 AMOC weakening tend to have both greater southwards OHT transport increase into
 526 the SO, and a greater SO temperature dipole magnitude.

527 The first group involves coupled ocean/atmospheric processes (and has some zonal
 528 asymmetry). AMOC weakening reduces northwards ocean heat transport across the equa-
 529 tor. Heat accumulates in the SH upper ocean, north of the ACC. This leads to the well-
 530 established ‘bipolar seesaw’ pattern of NH cooling and SH warming (Crowley, 1992; Stocker
 531 & Johnsen, 2003; Stocker et al., 2007). Meanwhile, atmospheric adjustments shift the
 532 SH westerlies southwards (also shown by e.g. Liu et al. (2017); Markle et al. (2017)). This
 533 southwards shift of the westerlies shifts the SO Deacon cell southwards. The Deacon cell
 534 change is partially compensated by a strengthened SO eddy circulation, in agreement
 535 with e.g. Chen et al. (2019). Some of the accumulated upper ocean heat is transported
 536 southwards across the ACC, predominantly by parameterised (eddy and diffusive) heat
 537 transports, in agreement with similar experiments under glacial conditions (Pedro et al.,
 538 2018). This anomalous heat transport into the SO region leads to ocean and atmospheric
 539 warming from the ACC polewards, eventually causing sea-ice melt.

540 The second group of processes is atmosphere-dominated (and has much stronger
 541 zonal asymmetry). A Rossby-wave-like pattern originates from Central America and prop-
 542 agates eastwards into the SO. Due to its origin over Central America, this teleconnec-
 543 tion is novel: previous studies have identified in response to AMOC weakening a ‘La Nina’-
 544 like teleconnection originating from a different location, the central Pacific Ocean (Timmermann
 545 et al., 2010; Orihuela-Pinto et al., 2022).

546 A full investigation of the tropical processes generating the teleconnection are out-
 547 side this study’s scope, but we suggest a possible source here. In the u03hos relative to
 548 the piControl simulations, we identify a strong positive meridional gradient in the at-
 549 mospheric relative vorticity at 200hPa (not shown). This gradient is strongest at $\sim 1^\circ\text{S}$,
 550 80°W , on the east coast of Central America, and indicates favourable conditions for Rossby
 551 wave generation (Lachlan-Cope & Connolley, 2006; Jin & Kirtman, 2009). The gradi-
 552 ent most likely arises from a combination of zonally asymmetric changes including (a)
 553 the net southwards shift of the ITCZ (Chiang & Bitz, 2005; Broccoli et al., 2006), lead-
 554 ing to warmer, wetter conditions particularly over the southern tropical ocean basins,
 555 and (b) a strengthened Walker Circulation and enhanced subsidence over the eastern Pa-
 556 cific and coast of Central America, which has been identified in a similar simulation (Orihuela-
 557 Pinto et al., 2022).

558 Previous studies of DO events have suggested distinct timescales for the evolution
 559 of a ‘slower’ bipolar mode, and a ‘fast’ atmospheric teleconnection (Stocker & Johnsen,
 560 2003; Markle et al., 2017). We cannot distinguish a clear time-separation between the
 561 evolution of the pressure dipole, and the circumpolar upper-ocean warming (Fig. S16;
 562 see warming from approximately $30\text{--}60^\circ\text{S}$); both begin within decades of AMOC weak-

563 ening, and progressively strengthen throughout the simulations. Much longer simulations
 564 might be required to identify two distinct timescales of evolution. We suggest that on
 565 multi-centennial timescales, the tropical changes that generate the teleconnection would
 566 settle more quickly than the longer-timescale heat accumulation in the SO from the bipo-
 567 lar seesaw process, which could take multiple centuries to mature (Stocker & Johnsen,
 568 2003; Landais et al., 2015; WAIS-Divide-Members, 2015; Pedro et al., 2018).

569 The magnitudes of SO temperature and sea-ice change in this study seem small rel-
 570 ative to some past events (WAIS-Divide-Members, 2015; Markle et al., 2017; Diamond
 571 et al., 2024; Holloway et al., 2018; Chadwick et al., 2023). SO mean SAT and SIA changes
 572 for most models are of a similar order to interannual variability (e.g. Figs S5-6). This
 573 is in some part explained by regional asymmetry (e.g. Fig. 2). Nevertheless, we show
 574 that these impacts are statistically significant and the processes that yield them are ro-
 575 bust across models (e.g. Figs 1 and 4). Furthermore, the centennial-scale DO-AIM ‘de-
 576 lay’ observed in ice cores seems consistent with our study: the relatively small changes
 577 we detect here on timescales of up to a century likely could not be resolved using ice core
 578 data (Pedro et al., 2018; WAIS-Divide-Members, 2015; Landais et al., 2015; Svensson
 579 et al., 2020).

580 Through this study, we used existing model output from the NAHosMIP CMIP6
 581 project, detailed and analysed in Jackson et al. (2023), wherein a large (0.3 Sv) fresh-
 582 water hosing was applied to the North Atlantic. Applying similar large freshwater hos-
 583 ing is a standard method of weakening the AMOC in GCMs, to investigate hysteresis
 584 and global AMOC weakening impacts, see e.g. Krebs and Timmermann (2007); Stouf-
 585 fer et al. (2006); Vellinga et al. (2002); Timmermann et al. (2007); Liu and Liu (2014);
 586 Jackson and Wood (2018a); Jackson et al. (2015); Kageyama et al. (2013). The NAHos-
 587 MIP experiments allow us to investigate multidecadal scale impacts of substantial AMOC
 588 weakening on the SO, comparing systematically across 8 CMIP6 models. We note that
 589 the forcing applied is much larger than North Atlantic freshwater forcing that could be
 590 expected under climate change (Van den Berk & Drijfhout, 2014; Jackson et al., 2023;
 591 Lenaerts et al., 2015). Despite this large North Atlantic forcing and substantial AMOC
 592 weakening, the SO responses we report are smaller than what might be expected over
 593 the next century due to future anthropogenic warming. For example, under moderate
 594 climate change scenario SSP1-2.6, northwards OHT is expected to increase by ~ 200 TW
 595 at 40°S and ~ 300 TW at 50°S (Mecking & Drijfhout, 2023). By comparison in Fig. 3(a),
 596 considering the multimodel range, southwards OHT increases by 50-150 TW at 40°S and
 597 0-50 TW at 30°S . Furthermore, mean SO temperature under SSP1-2.6 is expected to in-
 598 crease by 0.5-1.5C by the 2050s, relative to the present-day (Fox-Kemper et al., 2021);
 599 this is also larger than the SO 0.3°C increase in the ensemble mean that we report here.
 600 We note that the larger regional differences due to the atmospheric teleconnection we
 601 identify (e.g. multimodel mean SAT difference of 0.6°C , and greater for some models,
 602 see Fig. 2) are more comparable to the magnitude of greenhouse-gas-related changes.
 603 Overall, this tells us that the multidecadal-scale SO sensitivity to substantial AMOC weak-
 604 ening is much smaller than the multidecadal-scale SO sensitivity to more direct green-
 605 house gas-induced warming.

606 Although the two ‘groups’ of processes are similar across models, there are signif-
 607 icant inter-model differences in the magnitude of the SO temperature and sea-ice response
 608 (e.g. SO SAT warming is 0.2°C in EC-Earth3, versus over 1°C for CESM2). This is likely
 609 explained by inter-model differences in ocean representation and AMOC weakening. Whilst
 610 each of the models has a similar timescale and pattern of AMOC weakening, there are
 611 significant inter-model differences in AMOC initial and final states (Fig. S1 and Jackson
 612 et al. (2023)), so the models have different magnitudes of southwards ocean heat trans-
 613 port increase. This is supported by the relationship shown in Fig. 4: models with greater
 614 AMOC reduction tend to have a greater increase in southwards OHT into the SO. There
 615 are also inter-model differences in ACC strength and position (Mohrman et al., 2021);

616 Beadling et al., 2020), and the representation of mesoscale ocean eddies (Jackson et al.,
 617 2023), which largely control additional heat transport across the ACC (Beadling et al.,
 618 2020; Shi et al., 2021; Dufour et al., 2015). All models parameterise mesoscale eddies based
 619 on the Gent-McWilliams scheme. Here, the eddy-induced (advective) transport is a prod-
 620 uct of the eddy-induced transfer coefficient K and the slope of isopycnals S (Sec. 2.2.2).
 621 In these models, differences in magnitude of the additional eddy-induced heat transport
 622 across the ACC (identified in Sec. 3.2.2) may originate from inter-model differences in
 623 K , as well as from changes in S , and from the temperature contrast between the flows
 624 carried by the eddies southward and northward. It is outside this study’s scope to iden-
 625 tify which factors contributed the most, but we list them for a possible future study. Fur-
 626 thermore, models which instead have eddy-permitting ocean components tend to more
 627 effectively compensate a strengthened Euler circulation (Farneti et al., 2015). Therefore,
 628 eddy-permitting models would likely yield stronger eddy compensation under AMOC
 629 weakening, and even greater southwards OHT across the ACC.

630 In summary, future work could include: continuing these simulations for several cen-
 631 turies, or running longer lower-resolution model simulations. This would help identify
 632 whether the two ‘groups’ of processes have distinct timescales of evolution. Running en-
 633 sembles of simulations with each model would also help isolate these signals. The timescales
 634 and magnitudes of the SO response could also be constrained using observations of high
 635 temporal resolution, for past periods following significant AMOC weakening, e.g. DO
 636 or Heinrich events (Marcott et al., 2011; Broecker et al., 1992). The atmospheric adjust-
 637 ment processes that lead to the novel atmospheric teleconnection could also be further
 638 investigated. We showed eddy and diffusive ocean processes transport accumulated heat
 639 southwards across the ACC to high SO latitudes, but the model-dependence of these pro-
 640 cesses could be investigated in terms of model resolution and parametrisation – although
 641 the timescale of heat propagation likely also depends on other factors, e.g., initial and
 642 final states of the AMOC, and ACC strength (Jackson et al., 2023; Pedro et al., 2018;
 643 Markle et al., 2017).

644 5 Conclusions

645 Over the next century, significant AMOC weakening is likely (Fox-Kemper et al.,
 646 2021). It is vital to understand multidecadal-timescale impacts of AMOC weakening on
 647 the Southern Ocean (SO). However, there is no current consensus on these impacts (WAIS-
 648 Divide-Members, 2015; Markle et al., 2017; Orihuela-Pinto et al., 2022; Timmermann
 649 et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2019) and no studies have investigated the SO
 650 sea-ice response in detail.

651 We addressed this issue using the NAHosMIP CMIP6 model ensemble (Jackson
 652 et al., 2023). For the first time, we systematically assess, across a CMIP6 multi-model
 653 ensemble, oceanic and atmospheric impacts of substantial AMOC weakening on SO tem-
 654 peratures and sea ice. We explain the SO response in terms of two ‘groups’ of processes,
 655 which respectively cause more zonally uniform warming, and a temperature dipole with
 656 regional warming/cooling in the Indian Sector/Weddell Sea. The multidecadal temper-
 657 ature and sea-ice evolution is determined by a combination of these two groups of pro-
 658 cesses. Overall, the models share a similar multidecadal timescale for SO warming to be-
 659 gin. Over years 50–100, in the multi-model ensemble mean (multi-model range in brack-
 660 ets), the strongest ocean warming is in the Indian sector, at 200m to 500m depth along
 661 the ACC. The Southern Hemisphere westerlies weaken on the equatorward flank by 0.1
 662 to 1m/s, particularly in the Atlantic sector. Overall SO SLP decreases by 30 (10–70)Pa,
 663 SAT increases by 0.3 (0.1–0.7) $^{\circ}$ C, and SIA decreases by 0.4 (-0.2–1.3) Mkm^2 . The dif-
 664 ference between the Indian sector and Weddell Sea responses in SLP is 180 (80–320) Pa,
 665 in SAT is 0.6 (0.5–1.4) $^{\circ}$ C, and in SIA is 0.1 (0.1–0.2) Mkm^2 .

666 These impacts seem relatively modest: comparable for many models to the mag-
 667 nitude of interannual variability, and small relative to the changes expected under fu-
 668 ture anthropogenic warming. Nevertheless, these impacts, and the processes that yield
 669 them, are statistically significant and robust across models. Paleoclimate records and
 670 model studies suggest that on timescales of centuries to millenia, the weakened AMOC
 671 would lead to continued SO warming (of several degrees) and Antarctic sea-ice loss (on
 672 the order of a million km^2) (WAIS-Divide-Members, 2015; Svensson et al., 2020; Liu &
 673 Fedorov, 2019; Holloway et al., 2018). A substantial future AMOC weakening would have
 674 global consequences (Chiang & Bitz, 2005; Krebs & Timmermann, 2007; Broccoli et al.,
 675 2006), and we show through this study that these consequences extend to the SO and
 676 Antarctic sea ice on multidecadal timescales.

677 Open Research Section

678 The piControl CMIP6 DECK model outputs are in the ESGF archive: [https://](https://aims2.llnl.gov/search/)
 679 aims2.llnl.gov/search/. Information on obtaining this data available from [https://](https://pcmdi.llnl.gov/CMIP6/Guide/dataUsers.html)
 680 pcmdi.llnl.gov/CMIP6/Guide/dataUsers.html. For the piControl experiments, data
 681 is available at Danabasoglu et al. (2019); (EC-Earth) (2019); Boucher et al. (2018); Ri-
 682 dley et al. (2018, 2019); Wieners et al. (2019); Jungclaus et al. (2019); all last accessed
 683 July 2024. Processed model outputs used in this study are available at Diamond (2025).

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